

2025 NASA SMD Open Source Science Data Repositories Workshop

Versioning Decision Tool Concept - In-Person
August 25, 2025

- Facilitators: Candida Dewes
- Note-Taker: Rachel Slank
- Chat monitor:

ALL DAY MATERIALS CAN BE FOUND HERE

Agenda

- Visit each of five activity stations in small groups (online visit breakout rooms)
- A bell will ring to signal change to another station - mix up and join a new group
- Versioning Decision Tool Concept - Candida Dewes

Pre-Activity

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Comments and Discussions Heard During the Round Robin Sessions

- Is there a consistent consensus across all the DAACs
 - No, but we should
 - Some DAAC has their own flow charts and reasoning
 - Others don't
 - From a user side that would be very helpful, because going to each DAAC and seeing different things is not consistent and the user doesn't fully know what they are getting
- Who is driving the major decisions
- Biggest question on the chart is "what data values change"
- "Will it cause a scientific change in the data is too subjective"- we need more granular
 - Will it need a new DOI or is the original still good
 - This is an important question
 - The DOI part needs to be a separate question apart from the scientific change
- Every DAAC team needs to describe their pathways
- BPS is tied to the grant, so we don't run into the "data changed" often
 - It isn't going through stuff that is tens of years old
 - A new DOI isn't really needed because that is tied to the grants and papers

- But they should think about this just in case
- Every time we change something do we reach out to people?
 - “Hey I know you downloaded this data two years ago but we changed something” is that needed?
- This is a great start
- Product life cycle vs Mission life cycle would have different responses to this chart
- Integrate these trigger questions into Earth Data Pub
 - This is an important one
- How does DAAC versioning affect search results?
- How would you know that the science wouldn't change if the data change
- Changing the DOI would hurt published papers and that isn't fair to the authors
- In helio they don't change anything even when stuff changes and that drives me nuts but also it does change the science
- The science box needs to be removed
- You can declare the existence of something under a DOI, when you change something you should have a new DOI with a statement saying it is related to the old DOI
 - It is still that thing but it has evolved
 - How do you name it, version wise
- BPS changes the version with everything they change, so you can have 8 versions and it is not a problem
- What do you mean by remove data
 - Is it just moved
 - is it stored somewhere
 - Is it deleted forever
 - BPS had an example with the genome of DNA of astronauts, version1 had it version 2 does not because it is a protected info
- I like the idea of having this tree, but I wouldn't adopt this whole thing
- Remove the data– example of removing the calibrated data, but the raw data is still there, but a new DOI was created
- Minor change would be changing the meta data (fixing author name), would not need a new DOI
- Some of the lower questions on the trigger list can't just go right across, it needs to go up the other parts of the decision tree
- It is not in the authors benefit to have multiple DOIs, it splits credit (from person running the station)
- Is this anywhere published? It would be extremely useful to look at it a bit and then come back
 - There is a published AGU poster on zenodo
- This is very much in the weeds
- Are you trying to get to a common major and minor?
 - Yes and no, get more feedback in the decision
 - We have a process for major and minor this was more on how do we get there
- Has the data been downloaded? Has it been used?
 - If it hasn't then we change it without changing things or DOIs

- Metrics are important, look vs download vs published
- Is there external guidance on when to mint a new DOI?
 - Its subjective
 - Zenodo will make a new DOI no matter the change, minor or major
- What does a DOI for data mean?
 - Everything in planetary has a landing site and you can just update that
 - A lot of grey area right now and not a solid answer
 - In astrophysics, do I DOI every pixel?
 - Some people want that
 - Calibration errors wouldn't warrant a new DOI in planetary
- Would you list every DOI for every version?
 - People would need that for their publications
 - A list of DOIs is key with what was changed
- If you delete data with a DOI that science is not reproducible, which is the whole point of science
- Planetary has a plan for major and minor
 - Do you issue DOIs for minor versions
 - It depends, is it really really minor?
 - If something changes in the data a new DOI is issued
 - But a spelling error the author would not warrant a new DOI
 - That just is listed on the landing page
- The data being used is a key thing
- This is really comprehensive and we haven't thought about this at all
- Peer reviews of the data before it goes out
 - If there are new changes, does it need to be peer reviewed again?
 - If that answer is yes, it absolutely needs a new DOI
- How can you sure it has never been downloaded
 - Some places have metrics
 - Some have logins and are easy to track
 - Astronomy is anonymous, planetary is kind of both
 - Metrics can sort of tell but not really
 - Planetary will need to move to a login when it goes to the cloud
 - Need to know if bots are the only ones accessing it
- How will show up/ what will it say when it is a major or minor revision
 - Next to the title if it is a major version
 - Minor will show in the collection metadata
 - At least in the Earth Sciences
- Would like to have this system for BPS, because right now any single change warrants a new version
 - Even if it is just a period
 - Usually discussed between PI, POS, and Data scientist lead
- For internal use this is helpful, but for external/public, only scientific content deserves a new version
- Sometimes datasets are merged

- Do you keep one of the old names/ DOIs or is that a new thing all together
- If data is replaced, why is that minor change
 - The thought was a subset of data being replaced warrants it a minor change
- Input data is data that goes into making the dataset
 - If stuff in level one changes, all the other levels changes
- Conversation of citation DOI being added to data DOI
 - Literature citation (paper about the data)
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Webex Chat Comments

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Q&A

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